

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ФАКТОРЫ РИСКА РАЗВИТИЯ ОСТЕОПОРОЗА У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С РЕВМАТОИДНЫМ АРТРИТОМ

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RISK FACTORS FOR OSTEOPOROSIS IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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Аннотация

В данной диссертации исследуются факторы риска, способствующие развитию остеопороза (ОП) у пациентов с ревматоидным артритом (РА). Остеопороз, являющийся распространенным осложнением РА, значительно ухудшает качество жизни пациентов, их трудоспособность, повышает риск инвалидизации и смертности от переломов. В исследовании, проведенном на 261 пациентке в возрасте от 20 до 75 лет, изучены как традиционные, так и специфические для РА факторы риска, включая хроническое воспаление, положительную реакцию на ревматоидный фактор (РФ), терапию глюкокортикоидами (ГК) и менопаузу. С помощью клинических, лабораторных и инструментальных исследований измерялась минеральная плотность костной ткани (МПК) в поясничном отделе позвоночника, шейке бедра и предплечье. В исследовании подчеркивается, что пациенты с РА с большей продолжительностью заболевания, более высокими дозами ГК и пожилым возрастом подвержены повышенному риску развития ОП. Это подчеркивает важность ранней диагностики и необходимости профилактических мер, особенно у женщин в постменопаузе, для лечения и уменьшения последствий ОП. Полученные данные дают ценные сведения для улучшения лечения остеопороза у пациентов с РА и предлагают целевые терапевтические стратегии.

Abstract

This thesis investigates the risk factors contributing to the development of osteoporosis (OP) in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA). Osteoporosis, a common complication in RA, significantly affects patients' quality of life, work capacity, and increases the risk of disability and mortality due to fractures. The study, conducted on 261 female patients aged 20 to 75, explores both traditional and RA-specific risk factors, including chronic inflammation, rheumatoid factor (RF) positivity, glucocorticoid (GC) therapy, and menopause. Using clinical, laboratory, and instrumental assessments, bone mineral density (BMD) was measured in the lumbar spine, femoral neck, and forearm. The study highlights that RA patients with longer disease duration, higher GC doses, and advanced age are at an elevated risk for OP. It emphasizes the importance of early diagnosis and the need for preventive measures, particularly in postmenopausal women, to manage and reduce the impact of OP. The findings provide valuable insights for improving the management of osteoporosis in RA patients and suggest targeted therapeutic strategies.

Ключевые слова: Ревматоидный артрит (РА), остеоартрит (ОА), минеральная плотность костной ткани (МПКТ), глюкокортикоидная терапия, факторы риска.

Keywords: Rheumatoid arthritis (RA), osteoarthritis (OA), bone mineral density (BMD), glucocorticoid therapy, risk factors.

Introduction:

Due to the widespread nature of osteoporosis (OP), its severe complications, social importance, and the unfavorable prognosis for the course of the main disease, osteoporosis is one of the most critical issues in rheumatology both in our country and abroad. In all age groups of patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA), the frequency of OP in the population has been observed to increase. OP significantly affects the work capacity of patients with RA, leads to a decline in their

quality of life, and causes significant increases in disability and mortality due to fractures in the vertebral bodies and peripheral bones. Low bone mineral density (BMD) does not usually prompt a patient to see a doctor; it is the complications of OP, such as fractures, that make one think about its presence. However, the fracture is a late clinical manifestation of the disease.

At the same time, understanding the main factors contributing to the development of OP in RA can help improve diagnosis and assist in the implementation of preventive and therapeutic measures. The development

of OP in RA is multifactorial and involves many recognized risk factors. These factors include both traditional risks for OP and those directly related to RA. The latter include chronic inflammation, activation of cellular immunity, and an increase in the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, leading to a decrease in the functional activity of patients, the severity and duration of the disease, rheumatoid factor (RF) seropositivity, and erosive and destructive changes in the joints. However, the contribution of each of these factors to the development of OP in RA remains controversial. Among these factors, severe RA, significant functional impairment, and glucocorticoid (GC) therapy are assumed to be the most important.

Although the use of GC in RA remains unresolved, on one hand, GCs have a negative (suppressive) effect on bone formation, while on the other hand, they are strong anti-inflammatory agents that effectively suppress inflammation in RA patients, thereby helping balance risk factors like disease activity. Additionally, studies recognize the role of traditional risk factors such as advanced age, menopause, low weight, and low body mass index (BMI) in the development of OP in RA patients [M.J. Green, 2001].

Objective:

The objective of this study is to investigate the risk factors for osteoporosis and assess their contribution to the development of osteoporosis in rheumatoid arthritis.

Materials and Methods:

The study included 261 women aged 20 to 75 years. A comprehensive clinical, laboratory, and instrumental examination was performed on all patients. Each patient's anthropometric, socio-demographic, and clinical data, including traditional risk factors for OP and the condition of the joints, were recorded in a specially developed individualized thematic chart. To assess the course of the disease, the following indicators were used: DAS 28 for RA activity [M. Prevoo, 1995], functional class (FC) [M. Hochberg, 1992], and the presence of extra-articular manifestations and complications of RA [D. E. Karateev, 2008]. Functional impairment was determined using the HAQ (Health Assessment Questionnaire).

All patients underwent clinical and biochemical blood tests. Immunological studies included the detection of rheumatoid factor and C-reactive protein (CRP) using a highly sensitive method (hsCRP). X-rays of the distal parts of the hands and feet were performed on all patients. Erosion and joint space narrowing were calculated using the Sharp method modified by van der Heijde. BMD was assessed using dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry at the lumbar spine, femoral neck, and one-third distal part of the forearm. Bone density status was determined in accordance with WHO recommendations. For postmenopausal women, the T-score was taken into account, and for premenopausal women, the Z-score was used.

Clinical Characteristics of the Patients:

The control group consisted of 58 patients, with a mean age of 53 years. The duration of RA was 12 years (7-17 years). Erosive changes in the joints of varying

severity (stages III-IV) were identified in 93.6% of patients, while only 6.4% had non-erosive arthritis. The majority of patients were seropositive (86.2%). The mean DAS 28 value in the examined patients was 4.34 points. A low RA activity according to DAS 28 was found in 17.2% of patients, moderate activity in 51.7%, and high activity in 31.0%. Extra-articular manifestations were observed in 34.5% of patients. Most patients (60.3%) were classified as having severe functional impairment (HAQ score > 2), with 6.9% belonging to FC IV, 17.2% to FC II, and 15.5% to FC III. The mean functional index assessed by HAQ was 1.6 points. At the time of the examination, 51.7% of patients were receiving GC therapy. The duration of GC use ranged from 1 month to 36 months, with a mean duration of 18 months. The mean daily dose of prednisolone was 5 mg/day (3.75-10 mg/day). Of the participants, 25.8% were premenopausal, and 75.0% were postmenopausal.

Study Results:

In postmenopausal women, the prevalence of OP in the spine was 39.3%, in the femoral neck 37.2%, and in the forearm 58.6%. In patients with preserved menstrual cycles, the frequency of OP was statistically significantly lower in all skeletal regions compared to postmenopausal women, with OP more frequently detected in the femoral neck (17.2%) and the forearm (20.6%). OP in the lumbar spine was detected in 9.5% of cases. The analysis of BMD in different parts of the skeleton showed a statistically significant correlation between BMD in different parts of the skeleton in both premenopausal and postmenopausal women.

In 60.3% of women (group 1), OP was detected in the spine and/or proximal femur, while OP was not detected in the remaining 43% of women (group 2). Patients in group 1 were older, had longer RA duration, and had more pronounced destructive changes according to Sharp's assessment. Although DAS 28 values were comparable between the groups, patients with OP had higher hsCRP levels.

The average HAQ score was significantly higher in patients with OP: 43.1% of patients in this group had HAQ scores above 2, compared to 25.8% of patients without OP (relative risk (RR) = 1.90, 95% confidence interval (CI) = 1.22-3.02, $p < 0.002$). Patients in group 1 were on GC therapy for a longer period (70 (26.5-120) vs. 48 (11-79.5) months, $p < 0.01$) and more frequently took oral GCs (74% vs. 47.4%, RR = 1.7, 95% CI = 1.31-2.03, $p < 0.001$) and pulse therapy (41.2% vs. 17.5%, RR = 2.02, 95% CI = 1.12-3.09, $p < 0.01$). The total dose of GCs was higher (13.4 (5.22)-24.0 vs. 7.0 (1.5-14.4) g, $p < 0.01$), and the average daily GC dose for the past year was also higher (5 (3.5-8.8) vs. 3.55 (2.5-5) mg/day, $p = 0.002$) compared to patients in group 2.

Traditional Risk Factors for Osteoporosis:

When considering traditional risk factors for OP, it was found that patients with OP had lower body weight, with the majority of them being postmenopausal (90.9% vs. 65.4%, RR = 1.39, 95% CI = 1.2-1.61, $p < 0.0001$). Additionally, patients with OP were more likely to have had low-energy fractures (49.4% vs. 23.4%, RR = 2.17, 95% CI = 1.49-3.16, $p < 0.0001$). Moreover, periods of immobilization lasting more than

two months were significantly more frequent in OP patients (16.2% vs. 7.4%, RR = 2.30, 95% CI = 1.08-4.90, $p=0.02$).

Multivariate Analysis of Risk Factors for OP Development in RA:

To assess the influence of various factors on OP development in women with RA, a multivariate analysis was conducted. The analysis revealed that OP development in RA is determined by a number of variables, including menopause, history of low-energy fractures (excluding fractures of the femoral neck and vertebral bodies) (OR = 2.561, 95% CI = 1.194-5.495); HAQ-assessed functional impairment (OR = 1.642, 95% CI = 1.037-2.600); duration of RA (OR = 1.048, 95% CI = 1.003-1.096); and the average daily GC dose during the past year (OR = 1.304, 95% CI = 1.162-1.463). Other factors, including age, did not affect the risk of OP development.

Patients were divided into two groups based on the presence or absence of OP in the lumbar spine: 20 women (34.6%) had OP (group 1) and 36 women (66.4%) did not (group 2). Patients with OP were older than those without OP (59.8 ± 10.2 vs. 56 ± 11.1 years, $p=0.02$) and had more significant functional impairment (HAQ score > 2) (43.4% vs. 29.5%, RR = 1.47, 95% CI = 0.98-2.21, $p=0.05$). Patients with OP had been taking GCs for a longer period (72 (36-110) vs. 50 (12-95) months, $p=0.05$), had a higher average daily GC dose during the past year (6.3 (2.5-8.75) vs. 5 (2.5-7.5) mg/day, $p=0.01$), and had a higher total GC dose (14.4 (5.4-25.8) vs. 9 (2.4-16.5) g, $p=0.02$). The duration of the disease and RA activity based on DAS 28 did not differ between the groups. When analyzing traditional risk factors for OP, patients with OP had lower body weight (64.4 ± 10.6 vs. 69.2 ± 12.9 kg, $p=0.01$), and the majority were postmenopausal (94.6% vs. 74%, RR = 1.28, 95% CI = 1.14-1.42, $p=0.0001$).

Discriminant Analysis:

A discriminant analysis was used to assess the influence of various factors on the development of OP in the lumbar spine in RA patients. As a result, a predictive model was obtained, suggesting that the development of OP in the lumbar spine is determined by the functional impairment assessed by HAQ, the duration of RA, the average daily GC dose during the past year, and the presence of menopause. Weight had a protective effect on BMD.

Thus, the analysis allows us to conclude that the development of OP in the lumbar spine in women with RA is determined by the duration of the underlying disease (RA) expressed through functional impairment assessed by HAQ, the average daily GC dose during the past year, and the presence of menopause.

Risk Factors for OP Development in the Femoral Neck: The next step was to identify the factors associated with the risk of developing OP in the femoral neck, as femoral neck fractures are considered the most serious in terms of patient quality of life and prognosis. A comparison was made between two groups of patients: those with OP in the femoral neck (group 1, 20 patients (34.5%)) and those without OP (group 2, 40 patients (69%)). The age and onset of RA were comparable be-

tween the groups, but patients with OP had a longer duration of RA. Rheumatoid factor (RF) was detected in 69.1% of women in group 1 and in 54.8% of women in group 2 (RR = 1.3, 95% CI = 1.02-1.66, $p=0.04$). Quantitative assessment of radiological changes using the Sharp method revealed significant differences between the groups in terms of erosion scores (60 (7.5-112.5) vs. 16.5 (4-52) points, $p=0.02$) and joint space narrowing (117.5 (90-147) vs. 90 (52.5-121) points, $p=0.003$). During the past year, patients with OP had a higher average daily GC dose and received more intra-articular GC injections compared to those without OP. Evaluation of traditional risk factors for OP showed that patients in group 1 had lower body weight and BMI. In group 1, 86.7% of patients were postmenopausal, compared to 77.6% in group 2 (OR = 1.2, 95% CI = 1.06-1.36, $p=0.007$). In addition, patients with OP more frequently had first-degree relatives with a history of fractures (16.4% vs. 2.9%, OR = 5.57, 95% CI = 1.82-17.07, $p=0.001$).

Multivariate Analysis of Risk Factors for OP in the Femoral Neck:

An analysis was carried out to assess the influence of various factors on the development of OP in the femoral neck in RA patients. The analysis revealed that the main factors determining the development of OP in this part of the skeleton are radiological changes in the joints of the hands and feet (total Sharp score), the average daily dose of GCs during the past year, the total number of intra-articular GC injections, and the presence of menopause.

The results showed that the risk factors for OP development in the lumbar spine differ from those for OP in the femoral neck, which may be related to differences in the structure of bone tissue: cortical bone predominates in the femoral neck, while trabecular bone is more dominant in the spine.

Conclusions:

The development of OP in patients with RA is associated with both factors related to the disease itself (RA duration, HAQ-assessed functional impairment, and the average daily GC dose during the past year) and traditional risk factors for OP (menopause and a history of low-energy fractures).

Women with RA are at increased risk of developing OP, particularly in the lumbar spine and femoral neck. Therefore, densitometric examinations are recommended, and BMD measurements should be used to confirm the diagnosis of OP. The presence of OP in a given patient can be predicted based on established risk factors for OP in the spine (RA duration, functional impairment assessed by HAQ, the average daily GC dose during the past year, and menopause) and in the femoral neck (total Sharp score, RF positivity, the average daily GC dose during the past year, the total number of intra-articular GC injections, menopause, and the presence of fractures in first-degree relatives).

Preventive measures for women under 60 years of age who have never received GC therapy should primarily focus on reducing the influence of traditional risk factors for OP, such as quitting smoking, hormone replacement therapy (if not contraindicated), and physical therapy. Active treatment aimed at achieving RA

remission is necessary for younger women with a preserved menstrual cycle to prevent OP development, as the main risk factors for OP in this population are related to the disease itself (RA activity based on DAS 28 and the dose of GC at the time of the examination for patients taking GCs for at least three months).

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